

THE GENDER PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation. The article is committed to the orientation examination of the phraseological units of the Uzbek and English languages coding female insight. The creator apportions phraseological units with an clear orientation potential, phraseological units with female semantics and the phraseological units without huge orientation shading utilized for verbalization of the ideas of the female insight in two basically various languages. The design is to direct an orientation examination of Uzbek and English phraseological units that code the female knowledge. The examination philosophy joins a few techniques. The principle one is the spellbinding technique; different strategies incorporate perception, translation, correlation, speculation, and arrangement. Likenesses also, contrasts between the social and semantic world pictures were illustrated, in light of philosophical examination, correlation, and applied investigation of select definitions. An orientation portrayal of Uzbek and English phraseological units that code the female insight in the looked at languages is introduced. The investigation of expressions shows a high proportion of intellectually negative credits of the female insight in the brain of the agents of two fundamentally various languages. The viable worth of this exploration is that its outcomes can be utilized for various purposes: in follow-up semantic investigates, in investigations of orientation potential in manner.

Keywords: Phraseological unit; intellectual level; linguistic picture; gender analysis; similar value

Introduction. The genuine examination is committed to near considering of the set articulations assigning female insight as the principle lexico-semantic units mirroring a "orientation" code of the Uzbek and English languages and societies. The gender, orientation, orientation generalizations, orientation conduct energize analysts of different parts of sciences. Above all else, it reflects in mental investigates (Brandt, 1998). However, as of late the etymologists additionally showed extraordinary interest in this issue. The orientation generalizations are explored and become exposed in writing, diction, vocabulary, discourse conduct, and so on. The pertinence of the work is directed by need of examining of phraseological units coding female insight, and its epitomes in two structurally

different languages. Also, considering of the set articulations in the orientation plan has the significant hypothetical significance as discovery of compliances also, differentiations in two languages. It opens new information which can be helpful both at a clarification of language personalities, and at the arrangement of certain hardships of the interpretation.^[1]

Also, during a period of orientation explores, examining of a peculiarity "female knowledge" and its verbalization in language signs permits to form rather definitively acquired phonetic information on the concentrated on subject. The hypothetical significance of the work is in its commitment to the general hypothesis of mental phonetics. It advances further arrangement and considering of the issues associated with inquiries of relationship of language and thinking, language and culture, attitude of different countries, a language job in the course of information. Additionally, the consequences of examination can tolerate interesting to the interpretation hypothesis. The reasonable worth of the work is characterized by probability of purpose of the outcomes of genuine examination in different points: in further investigates on semantics; when creating courses of unique disciplines on concentrating on the manner; in mental semantics in Uzbek-talking and in English-talking crowds; and furthermore for showing the Uzbek and English languages in Russia and abroad. The consequences of exploration can track down application by drawing up course readings, manuals furthermore, reference books on an orientation potential in style. Moreover, in present day states of wide joining and common advancement of societies, the inquiry of need of an appraisal of the language peculiarities based on the relative examination gets the extraordinary worth. Phraseological units of any language bear in themselves all the width of the public idea, the experience of ages that is safeguarded for quite a long time (Hellinger and Motschenbacher, 2015; Dal, 2002). This material as nothing else brilliantly addresses the orientation generalizations put in an inner type of phraseological units. After all the orientation angle in articulation of the scholarly characteristics of female people by phraseological units (for this situation identical to the word or the expression) is exceptionally boundless discourse and cogitative peculiarity (Lapshina, 2008; Biri, 2005). The relationship of the female brain, mind, rationale, ineptitude stays a subject of relaxation talks and tattles all through hundreds of years. In this way, the orientation part of the scholarly movement reflects in layer of the Uzbek

¹ Alekseenko, M.A. (2006) Is the Image of Women Negative in Language? Moscow: Ellipse Publishing House. 263p.

and English phraseological units where the lady as the subject of cogitative movement and as the transporter of information gets some appraisal (Alekseenko, 2006; Soloveva, 2014). F. Kh. Tarasova (2012) in her monograph mentions that "the phonetic image of the world is shaped based on all language implies, for example, the word, the phraseological unit, the maxim, the text which contain foundation information and methods of impression of these qualities in the public picture of the world".

In the phonetic field there are various investigates on issues of a orientation separation Ye. S. Gritsenko et al. (2011), N. S. Solovyova (2014), H. Motschenbacher (2010). It is very regular, on the grounds that "for all normal individuals the qualification between the male and the female habits, propensities, gauges, portrayals, about what is acknowledged and allowable is very self-evident" (Ilyin, 2010). Further, utilizing and deciphering the got information, the etymologists effectively use them in various investigates. Elements of orientation generalizations becomes exposed in diction (Solovyova, 2014), the orientation in British and American lingvocultures is examined (Gritsenko et al., 2011). The etymological portrayal of ladies and men is considered by M. Hellinger and H. Motschenbacher (2015). The That's what creators notice "... the formal and utilitarian appearances of orientation in the area of human reference follow general, and maybe widespread standards in the world's languages" The genuine exploration sets as the reason a near contemplating of orientation highlights of the set articulations assigning female insight in the Uzbek also, English languages. The work manages the hypothetical and commonsense explores of a few logical bearings. As the material of this exploration served the Uzbek and English phraseological units, coding the female knowledge, chose by technique for nonstop determination of monolingual and bilingual phraseological word references, word references of the Uzbek and English adages and truisms. The procedure of examination addresses complex utilization of a few techniques. The fundamental is the graphic strategy including techniques for oversight, translation, examination, speculation and a tipologization. Likewise it is a strategy for the philosophical investigation of the picked definitions (insightful and inductive techniques), relative strategy, and furthermore the strategy for the applied examination lighting similitudes and qualifications of social and language photos of the world. These days while concentrating on the individual in the etymological image of the world the

enormous significance is acquired by individual attributes of the language character, the orientation worries to the most significant of them.^[2]

People are indistinguishable individuals by their tendency, yet, simultaneously, they can contrast on the certain highlights called "orientation highlights". Maybe new logical bearing called "orientation explores" manages the issues of orientation and gender. The immediate upkeep of the orientation generalizations in the different linguocultural networks can be considered through the language structures as orientation generalizations happen at all language levels and mirror certain appraisals. M. A. Alekseenko (2006) sees that, "the orientation point of view became one of the dominants of present day humanities, the particulars of male and female talks are considered, the generalizations of gentility and a manliness are laid out, and so forth." As indicated by A. G. Fomin (2003), orientation as "the psycholinguistic classification addresses multicomponent structure, the model of the social relations made by the really friendly organizations and built by people as per their orientation ID which is found in the language and the discourse". There are a few generalizations alleged "orientation generalizations", they are forced by society on the agents of male and female gender and are precisely recognizable in the language which, as we probably are aware, mirrors the person and culture of the transporters of any language. Orientation generalizations can be described as social and social perspectives on the attributes of character and principles of conduct impossible to miss to the male and the female commentators. These are sure convictions, conclusions, decisions. Various appraisals can be credited to something similar highlights relying upon what gender we give the trademark. "Orientation", or "gender" are the ideas which expect examining of the elements of the male and female reasoning, attitude, conduct. As per meanings of Brandt (1998), "gender" is a bunch of organic, physiological, regular signs, given by nature, and "orientation" is a bunch of the discourse, conduct, individual highlights recognizing people in the otherworldly arrangement who are submitted to the impact of societies. In ongoing examination A. M. Chervonnyiy (2014) apporions some semantic relations which are the foundation of an inside type of the phraseological units among which "a gender - a scholarly level". The lady as the subject of cogitative and scholarly action has both a positive and negative evaluation.

² Alekseenko, M.A. (2009) Who Discriminates against Whom in Language? The Horizons of Modern Linguistics. Moscow: The Languages of Slavic Cultures, 1532p.

In the investigation of the ideas "male psyche" and "female brain" it is important to think about various signs:

- the thoughts of individual and actual characteristics of the man and the lady in the way of life and society;
- the thoughts of their social significance and occupation (in the general public and in the family);
- the connection with the male and female beginning of the peculiarities, properties and relations which aren't associated straightforwardly with gender.

In the cutting edge world the negative evaluation of a thought of the lady in general and the female knowledge wins. The female astuteness is in quite a large number cases went against to male one, it is viewed as powerless, immature, unseemly to an ordinary human, and even ladies are here and there blamed for its nonappearance. "Idiocy" overall is particular to ladies, not men. Such amusing connection is utilized in assignment of the psychological capacities of the lady. It becomes conceivable to call a phraseological unit "женская логика" (a lady's explanation) (Idioms Usual and Unusual, 2007) a norm of the psychological illogicality. However, as indicated by M.A. Alekseenko (2009) "it is more catalyst to talk not about the separation in language, but rather the degree of man's or alternately lady's control".^[3] Along these lines, in the English and Uzbek phraseological units of the dissected field we uncovered the accompanying relationships:

- phraseological units with an undeniable orientation potential (one commentator – the lady), as per the designation of the female individual;
- the phraseological units with the female semantics utilizing ladylike lexics;
- the phraseological units without critical orientation shading applied to people of both gender.

It tends to be outlined with the examination of the phraseological units. As it was referenced over, the lexeme "баба" (lady) is a far reaching lexeme of the Uzbek language that is utilized to concern female people, that is the reason is orientation checked. The phraseological mix "базарная баба" (an uproarious lady) (Solovieva, 2014), for instance, portrays the female scholarly properties in a negative way as focuses to failure of ladies to act enough in broad daylight. It criticizes the female straightforwardness and extremism. In the English language the same articulation wasn't uncovered and the phraseological unit, comparable on esteem, isn't introduced. It tends to be made sense of by the uniqueness of a

³ Arsentyeva, Ye.F. (1999) Uzbek-English Phraseological Dictionary. Kazan: Heter, 536p.

beginning of phraseological units in each different mindset. The lexeme referenced above "баба" (lady) is likewise introduced at the level of phraseological mixes "бабье царство" (a lady's realm) and "бабье сословие" (lady's home) (Lapshina, 2008). The principal articulation implies a bunch, or a blockage of the ladies joined together, for instance, by the general occupation, along these lines, is orientation stamped. The subsequent articulation, as indicated by O.G. Lapshina (2008), is different esteemed: in the old signifying "женщины" (ladies) shapes a synonymic line with the phraseological units "слабый пол" (a more vulnerable gender), "нежный пол" (a delicate gender), "прекрасный пол" (a fair gender), "Евино племя" (Eva's clan), and so forth with an overall significance of "женщины" (ladies); in the second importance the phraseological unit "бабье сословие" (lady's bequest) - 'the ladies of low, unprivileged domain' structures outside equivalent words with the lexemes "бабы" (ladies), "простолюдинки" (basic ladies), "крестьянки" (workers). The two articulations, be that as it may, force to ladies the powerless insight because of the utilization of the lexeme "баба" (lady) that itself as of now makes a picture of the unpleasant and uninformed lady. In spite of the referenced phraseological unit the maxim "дамское сословие" (women's home) is introduced. 'The ladies having a place with world class, aristocratical areas of society' (Lapshina, 2008).

In the English phraseological circle we uncovered the articulation slip government (the mastery of a skirt), identical to the Uzbek adage "бабье царство" (a lady's realm) that, without a doubt, focuses to the orientation capability of this phraseological unit. Similar worries the maxim "слабый пол" (the more fragile gender), concurring to Ye.F. Arsenyeva (1999) the fair/more vulnerable/delicate gender as an English same of the phraseological unit the more vulnerable vessel. As we would like to think the property 'frail' is ascribed by physical as well as scholarly attributes. The accompanying gathering of the phraseological units of the Uzbek language is joined by utilizing of the lexeme "дура" (a senseless lady) in their design. These are the articulations like: "дура дурой" (Birikh, Mokiyeenko, and Stepanova, 1996); "дура набитая"; "петая (отпетая) дура" (a senseless lady in the two implications). As it follows from the implication of the multitude of articulations referenced the female people miss the mark on insight, they are senseless, dull, inept, and so forth. Here we can notice the solid orientation sign, on the grounds that "дура" (a senseless lady) is the female individual in Uzbek. To contrast it is conceivable with take the adage "дурья голова" (a senseless head) that as we would see it bears no orientation shading as it very well may be utilized in connection to people of both gender. In

the English phraseological reserve it is conceivable to express the shortfall of such kind of articulations as the word 'a dolt' doesn't have any genderual distinction. Considering the Uzbek phraseological units with respect to the orientation highlights, keeping away from the articulations with the lexeme "курица is incomprehensible (chicken/a hen). For instance, "умница", как пестрая курица" (clear head as diverse chicken) or "умница, как попова курица" (clear head as he minister's chicken). Both the articulations are orientation set apart as they utilize the lexemes "умница" (clear head - in Uzbek it alludes to a lady) and "курица" (chicken/ a hen) of a ladylike orientation. The blend of the referenced lexemes, in our assessment, gives a specific shade of incongruity to the phraseological unit. These articulations are normally utilized concerning the female people with low insight who make the senseless demonstrations, in regards to them to be right. Be that as it may, the Uzbek phraseological unit "слепая курица" (blind mole) (Arsentyeva, 1999), regardless of the presence of a similar lexeme of a ladylike orientation, isn't as we would see it orientation checked. In such a manner we can call the individual who sees severely, or didn't make anything out however it is all the more regularly utilized concerning ladies and it is associated with the effortlessness and intolerance. In English the comparative articulations were not uncovered.⁴

However, as we would like to think the phraseological unit "куриные мозги" (an empty head) that is a full semantic-grammatical likeness chicken's psyche, has female semantics, is generally utilized in assignment of the female ineptitude, extremism, infantilism. As indicated by Thalia (1996), this phraseological unit 'is pertinent not to any 'frail brain', but rather for the most part to the juvenile psyche, that is for the most part viewed as female brain'. Notwithstanding, it isn't important to endorse its orientation shading as the articulation can be appropriate to the people of both gender. The equivalent, as we would like to think, is seen in the articulation "курья голова" (chicken's head).

Conclusion. Set articulations that mean female knowledge are boundless in the examined languages; existing thoughts of the female brain are worldwide. According to the viewpoint of lexical-semantic quirks, the introduced material is a lexical field, wherein a bunch of articulations that signify the female knowledge can be recognized as a different class of units in the cutting edge Uzbek and

⁴ Birikh, A.K., Mokiyeenko, V.M., & Stepanova, L.I. (1996) The Uzbek Dictionary of Phraseological Synonyms. Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix. 363p.

English language, because of signs and correspondences, intended for this class. The investigation of phrases shows a high proportion of intellectually regrettable characteristics of the female knowledge in the psyche of the agents of two primarily unique languages. The viable worth of this examination is that its outcomes can be utilized for various purposes: in follow-up phonetic explores, in investigations of orientation potential in manner. Furthermore, under current broad combination and shared improvement of societies, the need of surveying etymological peculiarities, in view of a near investigation, turns out to be basically significant. Public interest in the female picture is ordinary of the cutting edge Uzbek and English language. Negative scholarly qualities win in the concentrated on material.

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